

Numerical analysis of plastic behaviour anisotropy of additively manufactured IN939 superalloy subjected to cyclic loading at high temperatures

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Abstract:

The Inconel IN939 superalloy is a suitable material for additive manufacturing. However, such a manufacturing process creates an anisotropic microstructure, which influences the material's mechanical performance. The effect of microstructure on fatigue behaviour at high temperatures is studied using the finite element method within the crystal plasticity framework. The spatial evolution of stresses and strains with cyclic loading is analyzed. The results show that material loaded perpendicularly to the building direction has higher strengthening and higher activity of slip systems in whole volume while loading parallel to the building direction induces plasticity, preferably in grains with (101) and (111) orientation. Such differences can lead to different damage initiation and evolution.

Keywords: FEM, crystal plasticity, IN939, cyclic loading

1. Introduction

Nickel-based superalloys have, in general, a superior combination of high-temperature mechanical properties and oxidation resistance [1]. Therefore, they are used in high-performance applications such as aerospace and energy production. Inconel 939 is a superalloy developed in the 1960s, and its outstanding high-temperature properties are caused by a large amount of reinforced γ' coherent phase inside the γ matrix [2][3]. However, the coherent phase is responsible for cracking at high temperatures and, therefore, limits the weldability of the Inconel alloys. IN 939, in particular, has “fair” weldability, which makes it suitable for additive manufacturing (AM) processes [4][5]. Their advantage is the production of final components, which can decrease material costs by 30% to 50% [6]. Different additive manufacturing technologies were applied on IN 939, such as selective laser melting (SLM) [7], electron beam melting (EBM) [8] and laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF) [9]. Microstructural studies have shown the difference between cast and AM produced IN 939, mainly the anisotropy in grain size and texture in AM material [10].

The mechanical properties were also extensively studied, including tensile and fatigue tests at a temperature range from room temperature to 900°C, proving that AM-produced IN 939 has similar or superior properties compared to its cast variant [11][12]. The detailed studies showed that the main deformation mechanisms at high temperatures comprise Orowan loops bypassing, anti-phase boundary and stacking fault shearing and deformation twinning [13][14].

The experimental studies of deformation processes are complemented by the numerical analysis that provides local information which the experiments cannot obtain. The mechanical properties of Inconel alloys have been numerically studied using different types of models. The macroscopic behaviour can be analyzed using models describing the global properties like yield stress, hardening, and mean stress [15][16][17][18]. The models also incorporate effects of microstructural features such as precipitates [19][20][21][22][23]. The more local approach takes into account grain morphology and applies the constitutive behaviour on the polycrystalline structure of particular materials such as additively manufactured IN 718 [24][25][26][27][28][29]. Models for high-temperature behaviour can also model the evolution of texture [30]. The evolution of stresses and strains inside the microstructure can be used for the assessment of critical points for damage initiation [31][32].

The current study is focused on the analysis of the high-temperature behaviour of L-PBF IN 939 alloy subjected to plastic cyclic loading. It describes the differences in local plastic behaviour caused by the different grain morphology and textures with respect to the loading direction. The numerical results are explained in the context of experimentally observed phenomena.

2. Material and loading

The investigated material is IN939 superalloy prepared by the L-PBF method. The alloy underwent three-step heat treatment (1160 °C/4 h, 1000 °C/6 h and 800 °C/4 h) for optimal high strength and ductility combination [10]. The microstructure of the material consists of elongated grains in the L-PBF process building direction (BD). The grains aspect ratio is about 10 in the building direction. The material has a strong <001> texture parallel to the BD. The EBSD images of microstructure in perpendicular and parallel directions to BD are shown in Figure 1.

The material was tested by cyclic loading with a symmetrical cycle ($R\epsilon=-1$) at temperatures 800°C and 900°C, representing a typical range of operating temperatures for these types of material. The loading was strain controlled with the total strain amplitude gradually increased after every 10 cycles by 0.05%. The material response to loading was tested in both orientations: “Perpendicular” – loading direction is perpendicular to the BD and “Parallel” – loading direction is parallel to the BD. More detailed information about material processing, microstructural characterization and fatigue behaviour can be found in [10][12].

Figure 1: EBSD images of microstructure of L-PBF IN939 superalloy with loading axis perpendicular to the BD (left) and parallel to the BD (right). Loading axis is vertical to the plane of EBSD image.

3. Finite element simulations

The numerical analysis is performed using the finite element method. The FE model is implemented into the software Z-set. The analyzed volume of material is represented as the polycrystalline aggregate with the grains' morphology similar to the observed one. The simulated polycrystalline aggregate contains 100 grains, and it was created using Neper software. In order to increase the statistical relevance of the results, three different aggregates with unique grain distributions were created. The 3D finite element mesh was created within each aggregate containing around 147,000 quadratic tetrahedral elements (c3d10) and 627,000 degrees of freedom. One representation of aggregate is shown in Figure 2a). Each grain in the polycrystal has a prescribed crystallographic orientation. The distribution of orientations corresponds to the experimental observations. Therefore, three groups of grains were created according to the crystallographic axis correlating with the L-PDF building direction: (100) grains, (101) grains and (111) grains. Out of 100 grains, in each aggregate, 90 belongs to (100) grains, 5 to (101) grains and 5 to (111). In each group, half of the grains have the corresponding axis precisely parallel with the building direction, and the second half has the axis randomly inclined within the interval 0-15°.

The boundary conditions represent polycrystalline aggregate inside the bulk volume. They are schematically shown in Figure 2b). All faces of the aggregates remain flat and parallel during loading. One face remains fixed in the loading direction, and the opposite has prescribed displacement. The two material orientations are represented by the rotation of the polycrystalline aggregate with respect to the loading conditions. The loading conditions replicate the experimental one. The displacement is set to create symmetrical tension-compression loading with increasing strain amplitude. The strain amplitude increases by 0.0005 after 10 cycles.

Material behavior is described by the constitutive model based on crystal plasticity for FCC (face-center cubic) lattice with active {111} slip systems family [33][34]. It combines cubic elasticity and plastic slip (γ) as described by the equation:

$$\dot{\gamma}^s = \left(\frac{|\tau^s - x^s| - r^s}{K} \right)^n \text{sign}(\tau^s - x^s) \quad (1)$$

where τ^s is the resolved shear stress in s -th slip system, x^s is the shear stress resulting from kinematic hardening, r^s is the critical resolved shear stress and constants K and n are parameters of Norton's viscoplastic law. The experiments show that studied material does not show isotropic hardening during cyclic loading, therefore its value is described by the constant initial value of critical resolved shear stress r_0 :

$$r^s = r_0 \quad (2)$$

The only hardening presented in the model is thus kinematic hardening that describes the shift of yield surface center during the cyclic loading and its equation is given as:

$$\dot{x}^s = C\dot{\alpha}^s, \dot{\alpha}^s = \dot{\gamma}^s - D|\dot{\gamma}^s|\alpha^s \quad (3)$$

with C, D being constant parameters.

Two sets of parameters are used to describe the material's behavior during loading at 800°C and 900°C, respectively. The elastic constants were obtained from the study of Keshavarz et al. [Keshavarz2016]. Parameters for critical resolved shear stress and kinematic hardening (C, D) are obtained by fitting the experimental cyclic curves using the simplified 125-grain polycrystalline aggregate with 1000 elements. The comparison of experimental and numerical cyclic stress-strain curves for both orientations is illustrated in Figure 2c). The parameters of the model are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters of the crystal plasticity constitutive model.

Elasticity					
Temperature [°C]	C_{1111} [GPa]	C_{1122} [GPa]	C_{1212} [GPa]		
800	195.0	129.8	101.4		
900	185.4	124.1	97.95		
Plasticity					
Temperature [°C]	n	K [MPa·s]	r_0 [MPa]	C [MPa]	D
800	10	5	67.3	2×10^6	7800
900	10	5	58.8	1×10^6	8500

Figure 2: a) Representation of the polycrystalline aggregate with FE mesh; b) Schematic illustration of boundary conditions for both loading orientations; c) Comparison of experimental and numerical cyclic stress-strain curves after fitting the parameters of constitutive model.

4. Results

Figure 3: Results of numerical analysis of cyclic loading of polycrystalline aggregates for different loading orientations and temperatures. Each curve represents aggregate: a) Cyclic stress-strain curves. b) Evolution of cumulated plastic slip with applied strain. The points on the curves represents the states that are used for detailed analysis of stress and strain distribution inside material

The evolution of stress and strain variables averaged over the whole polycrystalline aggregate is shown in Figure 3. The cyclic stress-strain (σ_{LD} - ϵ_{LD}) curves for each polycrystalline aggregate are depicted in Figure 3a). The material loading in the perpendicular direction has approximately 1.3 times higher hardening rate compared to the parallel direction for both temperatures. However, the overall stress level decreases with increasing temperature. The similarity of curves for individual aggregates proves that all three representative polycrystalline aggregates provide very close results. The stress-strain state inside the polycrystal is more complex and for the proper assessment of plasticity, the shear on slip system is a valid measure, because it can be related to the dislocation activity and possible damage accumulation. The overall activity of slip systems can be evaluated as cumulative plastic shear on all slip systems:

$$\gamma_{PCUM} = \sum_{i=1}^{12} \gamma_{PCUM}^i \quad (4)$$

where γ_{PCUM}^i is the cumulative plastic shear on each individual slip system in IN939. The evolution of cumulative plastic shear with respect to applied strain is shown in Figure 3b). The amount of cumulative plastic shear is higher in the perpendicular case even if its plastic hardening is higher. Increasing the temperature causes higher difference between both orientations, so the activity of slip systems increases furthermore in perpendicular orientation.

The stress-strain state inside the polycrystal can be investigated in more detail using the average values for each individual grain. The values of stress (σ^{GLD}) and strain (ϵ^{GLD}) in each grain relative to the average for the whole aggregate (σ^{ALD} , ϵ^{ALD}) at the temperature of 800°C are shown in Figure 4. The data are taken at applied amplitude of $\epsilon_{LD} = 0.005$, as indicated by the marks in Figure 3. This point is chosen as a limit case because some grains reach up to 30% of cumulative plastic slip, which can, in real structure, cause rotation of crystal lattice, which is not taken into account in the simulations. The perpendicular orientation (Figure 4a) shows that the stress-strain values for grains are spread within the interval of 0.5 -1.5 times the average and there is no significant difference between grains with different crystallographic orientations. The (101) grains and (111) grains have

higher stress and lower strain in general. However, there is no significant division into hard and soft grains based on their crystallographic orientation. The parallel orientation is shown in Figure 4b) and it has completely different distributions. The relative strain in grains is distributed in a narrow range (0.85 - 1.15) regardless of their crystallographic orientation. On the other hand, there are significant differences between their stress levels. The (100) grains are clearly the weakest orientation, having the stress level close to average, while (101) and (111) grains create the hard orientation with the stress 1.5 and 2 times larger than average, respectively. The results for temperature of 900°C are present in Figure 5. The limiting strain is $\epsilon_{LD} = 0.0035$ in this case, showing that plastic slip evolves to higher extent at higher temperature. However, the distribution of stress and strains is very similar to the one for 800°C. Therefore, local stress and strain evolution remains unchanged with increasing temperature. It can be stated that in the case of perpendicular orientation, the strength of the material is uniformly held by all grains, while for the parallel one, the strength is provided by the (101) and (111) grains and loading closely corresponds to isostrain conditions.

Figure 4: The distribution of average stress and strains for each grain of polycrystalline aggregate related to the average values for whole aggregate at a temperature of 800°C for a) perpendicular orientation and b) parallel orientation.

Figure 5: The distribution of average stress and strains for each grain of polycrystalline aggregate related to the average values for whole aggregate at a temperature 900°C for a) perpendicular orientation b) and parallel orientation.

5. Discussion

The experimental measurements show the different response of material on cyclic loading depending on its orientation. The perpendicular orientation has higher strengthening than parallel one, however the difference is about 30%. The most striking difference is in the overall fatigue life as illustrated in Figure 2c. The perpendicular orientation withstands cycling up to total strain amplitudes of 0.4% while parallel one up to 0.8% for 800°C and similar situation occurs at 900°C with total strain amplitude 0.6% for perpendicular and 1% for parallel orientation, respectively. Such a difference is a result of complex problem of fatigue damage initiation a growth followed by crack initiation a propagation. Applied numerical model is not able to describe such complex process in full scale, however it can be used for analysis of local stress/strain states with identification of spots for possible fatigue damage initiation. The difference between the fatigue life of the two orientation has roots in local conditions inside the polycrystal. Figure 3b) shows that plastic shear cumulates at higher rates in perpendicular orientation. The reason for such a difference can be identified by the analysis of stress and strain on the level of individual grains. The stress-strain distribution shows that in perpendicular orientation, there is no significant difference between grains stress/strain state regarding their crystallographic orientation, while in parallel orientation, there are large differences in stress level for grains with different orientation. Fatigue life is related to the evolution of damage which results from the combination of plastic strain cumulation and stress state. Therefore, the mechanical state of each grain is evaluated by the cumulated plastic shear, von Mises stress and stress triaxiality which is defined as:

$$\eta = \frac{(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})}{3\sigma_{vM}} \quad (5)$$

where σ_{ii} are diagonal components of stress tensor and σ_{vM} is von Mises stress. The cumulated plastic shear can be related to the accumulation of dislocations which can lead to anti-phase boundary and stacking fault shearing [14], von Mises stress describes the level of overall stress and stress triaxiality provides information about hydrostatic stress which plays role in voids growth.

The distribution of plastic shear, von Mises stress and stress triaxiality in individual grains for perpendicular orientation at the temperature of 800°C are illustrated in Figure 6. The (100) grains are in majority the least strained and stressed group, however there are several grains with high plastic shear, stress and triaxiality which can be very susceptible to initiation of damage by plastic strain accumulation and consequent growth of voids. The (101) grains are divided into two groups. The first one contains grains in similar state to (100) grains with lower stress and plastic shear level but average triaxiality. These grains are less prone to damage initiation. The other part of the (101) group, on the other hand, suffers high stress and plastic shear, but with low triaxiality close to the pure shear conditions. These grains can be subjected to shear bands accumulation and subsequent shear damage. Similar conditions can be found for (111) grains which have in general highest stress and plastic shear level and the lowest triaxiality. Therefore, they can act as places of shear damage initiation.

The parallel orientation develops different stress/strain distribution. The (100) grains have low stress and plastic shear level with wide range of triaxiality, therefore it can be expected that they will not serve as primal damage initiation spots. The exception could be few grains with high triaxiality when the secondary particles are present. The high stress and high plastic shear are typical for (101) grains and even more for (111) grains. These grains are also subjected to moderate triaxiality. Therefore, they are most likely primary locations for damage initiation which can be combination of slip bands and void growth. Data for 900°C shows the same trend and the above analysis can be applied to them.

An overall comparison shows that in the case of perpendicular orientation the critical spots for damage initiation are distributed over larger volume and covers conditions for shear as well as void growth damage. On the other hand, in parallel orientation only grains with (101) and (111) creating approximately only 20% of volume are susceptible for damage initiation by mixed mechanism depending on local conditions. Larger volume of critical spots is probably dominating factor for significantly lower fatigue life of perpendicular orientation as shown by the experimental observations [11][12].

Figure 6: Distribution of average values of cumulative plastic slip and a) von Mises stress and b) stress triaxiality in grains inside the polycrystalline aggregates loaded in the perpendicular direction at the temperature of 800°C.

Figure 7: Distribution of average values of cumulative plastic slip and a) von Mises stress and b) stress triaxiality in grains inside the polycrystalline aggregates loaded in the parallel direction at the temperature of 800°C.

6. Conclusions

Finite element simulations of low cycle fatigue loading of L-PBF manufactured IN939 polycrystal have been performed using the framework of crystal plasticity. The effect of material orientation on stress/strain state inside the polycrystal have been studied. The following conclusion can be drawn from the analysis:

- The material orientation has impact on cyclic mechanical behavior. The perpendicular orientation has higher hardening, but also experienced higher activity of slip systems.
- The stresses and strains are evenly distributed inside the grains in the perpendicular orientation.
- The parallel orientation has distinct differences in strength of different grains with the highest strength for (111) oriented grains and the lowest strength for (100) oriented grains.
- The damage evolution strongly depends on materials orientation. The perpendicular orientation has possible damage hotspots developed in majority of the volume and shear and/or void damage could be initiated. The parallel orientation develops possible damage hotspots in (101) and (111) oriented grains with damage mode combining shear and void initiation.
- Increasing the temperature will increase the overall amount of plastic slip with cyclic loading, but does not have an effect on stress and plasticity distribution inside the polycrystal.

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